

Alterations Appeared in The Hopping Length of Zinc Doped Nickel Ferrite System Driven by The Gamma Radiation Effect

Shaikh Asif Karim & Sayyed Mujeeb Hadi

Dept of Physics, Sir Sayyed College, Aurangabad

Corresponding Author – Shaikh Asif Karim

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19827083

Abstract:

A systematic investigation of structural, electrical, magnetic properties of Ni-Zn ferrite before and after gamma irradiation is carried out. Samples of spinel ferrite having the generic formula $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$ with $x = (0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0)$ were prepared using the standard ceramic technique. The samples of Ni-Zn ferrite were irradiated with gamma rays using Co^{60} source at the laboratory. Gamma irradiation alters the structural properties of Ni-Zn spinel ferrites. The distance between magnetic ions i.e. hopping length at tetrahedral 'A' site and octahedral 'B' site is then studied.

Keywords: Ferrite, Hopping Length, Gamma Radiation.

Introduction:

The polycrystalline spinel ferrite are well-known magnetic materials and are very useful in microwave applications, high quality filters, antenna rod, transformer cores etc.[1-3]. The property of magnetic conductor and electrical insulator made them useful in many of application. The properties like structural, electrical and magnetic are known to be sensitive to the chemical composition, microstructure, type and amount of dopant [4, 5, 6] etc. The substitution of zinc in nickel ferrite modifies the properties of nickel ferrite which are useful in many device applications. Thus nickel-zinc is an important mixed spinel ferrite. Irradiation effect provides several interesting and unique aspects in understanding of damaged structure and thereby modifying the properties of ferrite materials. Effect of γ radiation of Co-Zn on the structural properties has been reported by Hamada [7]. It has been reported that the physical properties of Ni, Zn, Cu spinel ferrite are also affected by irradiation. The structural, electrical and magnetic

properties of Ni-Zn spinel ferrites have been reported in the literature [8, 9, 10].

Experimental Setup:

Samples of spinel ferrite having the generic formula $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$ with $x = 0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0$ were prepared using the standard ceramic technique. The pure oxides (NiO, ZnO and Fe_2O_3) of 99.9% purity were used. The powders were mixed in stichemic proportion and ground to obtain a very fine powder. The powder was then heated/ sintered at $900^{\circ}C$ for 12 hrs. The sintered powder was again ground and palletized to room temperature for 24 hrs. They were polished to obtain a disc with two uniform parallel surfaces. The powder X ray diffractogram is used in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° at room temperature. The data was collected at room temperature.

The samples of Ni Zn ferrite were irradiated with gamma rays using Co^{60} source. All the properties were investigated before and after gamma radiation.

The distance between magnetic ions i.e. hopping length at tetrahedral ‘A’ site and octahedral ‘B’ site are calculated using the following relation 1, 2.

$$L_A = \frac{a\sqrt{3}}{4} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$L_B = \frac{a\sqrt{2}}{4} \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The values of hopping length are given in Table 1. The variation of hopping length with composition ‘x’ is depicted in Fig. 1.

Result And Discussion:

Since hopping length depends on the lattice constant, we observed the change in the hopping length before and after radiation [11]. As lattice constant increases the hopping length also increases with Zn substitution. The change in the structural properties after gamma irradiation of presently investigated samples is because that after irradiation, the stored energy of material increases and then it is released at the defects which are already exist. This results in decrease in the number of defects consequently the structural properties like lattice constant, X-ray density, particle size decreases.

Table 1: Hopping length (L_A) and (L_B) of before and after γ -irradiation of $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$

Composition ‘x’	L_A (Å)		L_B (Å)	
	Before	After	Before	After
0.0	3.613	3.610	2.950	2.948
0.2	3.620	3.618	2.956	2.954
0.4	3.628	3.626	2.962	2.960
0.6	3.636	3.634	2.969	2.967
0.8	3.644	3.642	2.976	2.973
1.0	3.652	3.649	2.982	2.979

Fig. 1: Variation of hopping length (L_A & L_B) with composition for $Ni_{1-x}Zn_xFe_2O_4$

References:

1. S. Krupanicha, (1976) “*The physics of ferrites and magnetic oxide related to them.*” (Russian translation) Moscow Min 1st Ed.
2. A. T. Neo and M. P. Pileni, (2001) *J. Phys. Chem B* 105 53.
3. P. Didukh, J. M. Greneche, A. Slwska-Waniewaska, P. C. Fannin and L. I. Casa, (2002) *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 242 613.
4. K.K. Laroia and A.P.B Sinha, (1963) *J. Pure Appl. Phys.* 1 215
5. A.M. Varaprasad and C.M. RadhaKrishnamurthy, (1986) *Bull Mat. Sci.* 8 567
6. K. Sailakshmi, P (1997).*h.D. Thesis, Andhra University India*
7. I. M. Hamada, J(2004). *Magn. Magn. Mater.* 271, 318.

8. P. B. Pandya, H. H. Joshi, and R. G. Kulkarni, (1991) J. Mat. Sci. 26, 5509.
9. Li Yao, Jiupeng Zhoo, Jiecai Han, (2002) Bull. Mat. Sci. 25 263.
10. D. C. Khan, M. Misra and A. R. Das, (1982) J. Appl. Phys. 53,2722
11. Shaikh Asif, Ph. D. Thesis – Effect of gamma radiation on physical properties of ferrite.